

Condensation Products of Dehydroacetic Acid with Some Primary Amines

D. E. Gupta and R. S. Gupta

It has already been reported that dehydroacetic acid(I) exists in solution as an enolised species (II), the carbonyl group of which at C₃ condenses with the amino group of primary amines and amino-acids, yielding products to which has been assigned the structure (III) (where R = PhN etc).

(I)

(II)

(III)

In the present communication, the same work has been extended with *n*-butylamine, *o*-bromoaniline, *p*-iodoaniline, *m*-toluidine, *o*-chloroaniline, 2-methyl-4-iodoaniline, *p*-aminobenzoic acid, 2,3-dichloroaniline, *p*-aminosulphonic acid, 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid, *o*-nitroaniline, *m*-nitroaniline, and with two primary diamines, viz., *n*-phenylenediamine and benzidine.

Procedure.—The condensations were carried out in the same way as described earlier¹.

Primary amines (0.01*M*), dehydroacetic acid (0.01*M*; 0.02*M* in case of diamines) and ethanol (20 ml) were refluxed over a water bath for about 4 hr. The reaction mixtures on cooling yielded solid products which were recrystallised from ethanol. The reaction of benzidine with dehydroacetic acid was, however, complete within 20 min. The characteristics of the condensation products obtained are recorded in Table I.

Incidentally, *o*- and *m*-nitroanilines did not yield any condensation products even though the reaction mixtures were refluxed for 10-12 hr. in presence of sodium acetate. This may probably be due to their extremely weak basic nature.

¹ Gupta and Gupta, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 421.

TABLE I

Primary amine.	Formula of the product.	% Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	22	60°	Yellow	6.24%	6.27%
<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ NBr	58	159°	Dirty white	4.30	4.34
<i>p</i> -I.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ NI	60	193°	Cream-yellow	3.73	3.79
<i>m</i> -Me.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	59	123°	Cream-yellow	5.39	5.44
<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ NC1	72	156°	Dirty	4.91	5.04
2-Methyl-4-iodo-aniline	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ NI	55	155°	White	3.62	3.66
<i>p</i> -HOOC.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	49	248°	Dirty white	4.62	4.88
2,3-Dichloro-aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ NC1 ₂	25	173°	White	4.46	4.49
* <i>p</i> -HO ₃ S.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₆ NS	40	..	Dirty	4.61	4.64
*1-Amino-2 naphthol-4-sulphonic acid	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₇ NS	47	..	Chrome-violet	3.53	3.57
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂	41	206°	Dirty	6.81	6.86
H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ .C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₂	80	271° (decomp.)	Yellow	5.72	5.79
<i>o</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	No reaction					
<i>m</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	No reaction					

*Does not melt.

One molecule of benzidine or *m*-phenylenediamine was found to react with 2 molecules of dehydroacetic acid to yield condensation products which have been assigned the structures (IV) and (V).

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